

The EnCycLEd Project Promotes “The Importance of Cybersecurity Education for Leveraging the Development of AI-based Decision Systems”

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Abstract

The EnCycLEd project¹ (*Enhancing Cybersecurity Literacy in Education*) aims at improving awareness of cybersecurity threats and opportunities among students, individuals and organizations. This way, the project fosters digital security readiness and resilience by providing cybersecurity educational programs and resources, encouraging also the interest in cybersecurity studies and career pathways. Hence, the project leverages digital skills among students and inspires the next generation of cybersecurity professionals to be better prepared to develop safer systems, including AI-based decision systems.

The project boosts digital readiness and cybersecurity resilience for educational. It focuses on equipping students, teachers, and educational professionals with key digital skills and competences. As key elements, the project develops educational curricula and a platform, which include: cybersecurity fundamentals; practical defence skills and critical thinking; interactive games simulating real-world challenges; interviews with insights from cybersecurity experts; simulation exercises in real world scenarios; as well as pathways and study options to assist teachers in guiding students' career choices. The EnCycLEd web-platform counts with a curated resource collection of the produced material for the curriculum and provides a trusted space for the development and sharing of educational materials, prioritizing safety and security.

The project will be validated at various educational institutions, focusing on collecting feedback and on evaluating the project's impact. For this, the EnCycLEd partners will conduct training sessions, workshops, and presentations for both teachers and students. This includes developing didactic workshops and pilot programs. Additionally, the developed toolkit will be tested within the EnCycLEd platform at the pilot-schools.

In conclusion, cybersecurity awareness is essential in education to protect data, promote responsible AI use, and prepare students for digital threats. The EnCycLEd project fosters a culture of safety and ethics in technology, raising awareness among students and teachers to avoid cyber threats and ensure data privacy, especially in the development of AI decision systems.

Keywords: Cybersecurity Awareness; Erasmus+ Project; Education; Digital Readiness; Cybersecurity Training

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